

Legal Implication of Copyright Protection to Artificial Intelligence and Its Impact on Economic Growth

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Raghavendra Sanjeevarao

Research Scholar at CMR University and Lawyer

Abstract

It is evident that Artificial intelligence is taking over the world and automation is affecting the individual(s) in all segments of commercial world. Under intellectual property rights' law regime, the endeavour of law is to protect the intellectual contribution of humans than anything else. It is a settled view that the skill, labour, judgement are conditional precedent for knowledge creation vis-à-vis its legal protection under various intellectual property protection laws like patent, copyright, trademarks, etc., There is no doubt that humans create machines but the fact that artificial intelligence is taking over the human mind cannot be denied. The machines are on the contrary contributing intellectual creations, which are perfect than human creations. One of the key issues arises for consideration is whether legal protection of such original creations by non-human artificial intelligence needs effective legal protection under IPR legal regime.

This paper seeks to study the problems arising out of intellectual property creation by artificial intelligence and its legal protection as well as legal liability under various laws more specifically intellectual property laws like copyright law in India. The study is based case laws and including judicial interpretation pertaining to copyright law on non-human intellectual property creations. The author concludes that by providing effective legal protection to the intellectual creations by non-human AI indeed has the impact on the economic development of the Country.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Copyright, Economic Development, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), DRM, ACL, Justice, Law, Legal Enforcement.

“The rise of the machines is here, but they do not come as conquerors, they come as creators”

- Andres Guadamuz

Introduction

One of the greatest inventions of the 20th century is Computer and Internet and its extensive use has given rise to innumerable and innovative technologies. The conflict between mind and machine has been co-existed along with the dawn of very computer technologies. Over a period of time learning machines have made computer no more a tool and it has gone beyond human expectations. No doubt algorithms and learning machines have not only become

an intrinsic part of human life but have become an ultimate source of creativity, accentuating learning, thinking and economic growth.

The outdated nature of the present Copyright Laws across the globe fails to accentuate the this contemporaneous realism, resulting into release of AI generated works into the public domain, thereby causing great amount of loss to those who invest huge money. This ongoing trend definitely does not, in any way advantageous to the programmers and owners of AI devices, and invariably hinders them to invest resources in the development of AI and hence affects technological and artistic progress of modern society and also affects the access of valuable works by the scholars, researchers, and consumers.

Literature Review: Lawrence Lessig : The author believes each generation has delivered a technology better than the last, the ability of the copyright holder to protect her intellectual property has been weakened. Author points out that the copyright has always been at war with technology however author envisions the belief that intellectual property cannot be protected in cyberspace, is wrong. Kalin Hristov : Author finds that the authorship of copyrightable works has been a 200 years of contentious history in the American legal system. Computer algorithms and learning machines have become a new source of creativity and booming AI has resulted more and more creative works without human intervention, which has accentuating the significance of AI as non-human author. Author points out that the U.S. Copyright Office has denied the copyrights of non-human works and releasing them into the public domain. Author argues that giving authorship to AI programmers and owners is essential to the future development of the AI industry as well as continues promotion of “the progress of science and useful arts”. Gönenç Gürkaynak, İlay Yılmaz, Türker Doygun, and Ekin Ince : Authors points out that the intelligent machine systems are transforming the lives for the better and more the capable machines, the world becomes more efficient and consequently richer. As the neuroscientists are still working on unlocking the secrets of conscious experience, authors argues once we consider machines as entities that can perceive, feel and act, it’s not a huge leap to ponder their legal status. On the whole technological progress means better lives for everyone. Artificial intelligence has vast potential, and its responsible implementation is up to us. Andres Guadamuz: argues that the manner in which the law tackles the machine-driven creativity could have far-reaching commercial implications. Though the precise impact on the creative economy is it difficult to ascertain, it will have a chilling effect on investment in automated systems.

Meaning and Scope of Artificial Intelligence

Etymologically the term AI was coined by John McCarthy in 1956 who is considered as the father of AI, defines AI as “the science and engineering of making intelligent machines”. AI is not only real but is it pervasive accentuating in all spears of life.

The growing body of works generated by computers includes such as ‘a short novel written by a Japanese computer program in 2016 reached the second round of a national literary prize’ . ‘The Google-owned artificial intelligence (AI) firm, Deep Mind, has created software that can generate music by listening to recordings’. ‘Computers writing poems , ‘editing photographs’ , and ‘composing music or generate works in music’ , ‘journalism’ and ‘gaming’ , and these works could in theory be deemed free of copyright because they are not created by a human author, that apart AI is capable of ‘composing art and music, it us also used in information management, Speech recognition, robotics, optimizing logistics, detecting fraud, conducting research, providing translations etc.,’

Legal implications for copyright law: Copyright is a type of IPR protection that helps to protect the intellect of human creation. Copyright law provides exclusive and monopoly right to the creator/author/owner of “original” literary, dramatic, musical, artistic works, cinematograph films.

Creating works using artificial intelligence could have very important implications for copyright law. Legal Definition of Author: Like Hong Kong, Ireland, New Zealand and the UK in India defines “author” in relation to any literary, dramatic, musical or artistic work which is computer-generated, is the person who causes the work to be created. Computer-generated works impetus on the creative input of the programmer, where the machine is used as a mere tool.

Copyright protection to AI works - issues and concerns: Artificial intelligence can produce self-sufficient systems that are capable of learning without human programming, the built-in algorithm allows it to learn from data input, and make dependent of independent decisions. The authorship or ownership under copyright law across the globe is “Human Centric” even in case of anonymous works the law contemplates human identification to attribute the ownership on the original works. Critical issues are who owns AI works, whether copyright protection can extend to non-human AI generated works? and what are the legal and economic implications if the legal protection under copyright law is not extended to AI works?

Non-Human Works and AI – Lawless laws

The settled position of law is non-human elements are excused of all legal rights and responsibilities. In *Naruto v. Slater* one David Slater, a British wildlife photographer, left his camera unattended and an Indonesian monkey named as “Naruto” by “PETA”, picked up the camera and clicked amazing selfies, which later went viral on the social media. Gentleman’s Quarterly and other magazines sought to feature Naruto in their publications. People for the Ethical Treatment of Animals (“PETA”) sued Mr. Slater and his publishers for copyright infringement. But the court dismissed the suit on the ground that Naruto did not own the copyright to the photos. Applying the said judicial principle it is clear that even AI which is a non human like that of Naruto cannot claim copyright to its creative original output as well as AI or its programmer cannot even claim ownership in the absence of human skill in the creation of original content. This thought process will have a serious ramifications on the persons or entities in not employing AI with a huge investment as they may not reap benefits under copyright law, and even if there is investment, invariably the original work may become part of public domain and initiating legal action against infringement becomes futile exercise.

Legal Personality of Artificial Intelligence

IPR across the world do not provide an effective legal norm with respect to the owning the original content created by AI, AI is born mature and it is real and pervasive as the world is becoming more tech savvy, the day is not far we become more AI dependent, hence there is a absolute need to improve our legal norms to give impetus to new way of original creativity accentuated by AI and treat AI as a legal person like personhood attributed to Idol, Corporate entities etc., in a conventional sense.

Impact of absence of copyright protection to AI

Failure to protect AI could have far-reaching commercial implications, though it is difficult to assess the exact commercial impact, it may have shocking effect on the investment in automation systems. The Automation system Music, gaming and journalism and other works stated above generated by Artificial intelligence are deemed to be free of copyright, as they are created devoid of human author, which is a bad news for the sellers of the said content, it is to be noted even if the content created by AI is DRM protected, still circumvention of DRM of such AI content may not amount to crime as there is no copyright subsists.

The US, Australia and EU copyright law protects only “the fruits of intellectual labor” that “are founded in the creative powers of the mind” and hence the “content generated with the intervention of a computer could not be protected by copyright because it was not produced by a human”. Further that the “copyright only applies to original works, and that originality must reflect the “author’s own intellectual creation.”

Conclusion with Suggestions

In the absence of proper norms or amendment of existing IPR legal regime to include copyright protection to the content created by AI, may hinder the growth of science and technology promised by the AI. It is to be further appreciated the existing copyright regime in India was amended to include Anti circumvention provisions by virtue of 2012 Copyright Amendment Act by introducing new rules in favor of Digital Rights Management by the owners of the copyrighted works. The said DRM and its breach itself amounts to violation of law and the said acts of its breach without payment of royalty can land up the culprit in jail. The DRM rules across the world has been criticized on the ground that the same limits the access to content unless royalty is paid, which hinders the knowledge growth.

Granting copyright to the person who made the operation of artificial intelligence possible is a practical approach, which ensures continues investment in the technology and gets returns. Considering AI as a legal person is also an option with limitations, which is imperative in view of enhanced computer capabilities, humans are no longer the only source of innovative and creative works. Protection always provides incentive to the creators. It is rightly said that all predictions of steady, exponential growth in computer power have to be duly qualified. Countries like New Zealand, Ireland, South Africa and the UK have decided to give copyright to the person who made possible the creation of procedural automated works, which is a welcome move.

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